

AUDIENCE EXPOSURE AND ADHERENCE TO THE NATIONAL AGENCY FOR PROHIBITION OF TRAFFICKING IN PERSONS (NAPTIP) FACEBOOK CAMPAIGN AGAINST HUMAN TRAFFICKING IN ANAMBRA STATE

¹Nnatu-Adoro Chiamaka Victoria and ²Prof. Cornelius Aghadiegwu Ukwueze

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Abstract

Human trafficking affects people of all races, religions, social classes, and education levels and often results in mental health disorders and life-threatening infections. It has existed in various forms in many parts of the world but was not considered a serious social problem until recent official discourses and media reporting. With media reporting of the crime in different parts of the world, including Nigeria's Anambra State, came media campaigns against the crime from different sources, one of which is the NAPTIP. Since the NAPTIP Facebook campaign is targeted at media audience/users, this study sought to determine the audience's level of exposure and adherence to NAPTIP's Facebook campaign against human trafficking. The descriptive survey design was adopted to achieve the objectives, while the 400 samples that were studied were selected using the multi-stage sampling procedure and the formula- $R = I \times S/N$ to ensure the proportionality of the samples. In the analysis of the study findings, frequency tables, simple percentages, and the arithmetic mean of the respondents' responses were used. The findings revealed, among others, that the level of exposure of Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking is very high. In view of the findings, it was recommended, among others, that Anambra residents should always have the quest to know more about human trafficking as that will make them keep track of media campaigns against human trafficking.

INTRODUCTION

¹Department of Mass Communication, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

²Department of Mass Communication, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State Nigeria

Human trafficking has existed in various forms in many parts of the world but was not considered a serious social problem until recent official discourses and media reporting (Weitzer, 2014). Slavery, the precursor of human trafficking, became an issue in the 19th century following advances in transportation and technology, which resulted in increased migration rates (Ezeh & Oli, 2021). According to them, with industrialization came the migration of people from rural to urban areas. Technological advances of the 19th century helped bring about the new and greater international mobility of labor, making it possible for traffickers to react quickly to the growing demand for sex trade and cheap labour (Badejo, 2016). The beginning of mass migration and technological development is significant because it has continued to the present (Ezeh & Oli, 2021). They stated that technological advancement and globalization enabled and encouraged people to migrate to places with better economic and social opportunities and made it easier and more efficient for those involved in the trafficking process to network and operate more efficiently.

Within Nigeria, girls are trafficked primarily for domestic servitude and commercial sexual exploitation, whereas boys are trafficked for forced labour in street vending, agriculture and as domestic servants (United States Department Report, 2009). Besides prostitution, forced marriage and forced labour, some of the victims are used for rituals, begging, and even organ transplantation (Ndifon, Apori & Ndifon, 2012).

To put an end to the above practices, the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) embarked on a Facebook and Twitter (X) campaigns against them. According to Sasu (2023), Nigeria had 31.6 million active social media users as of January 2023; therefore, this study sought to ascertain the audience level of exposure and adherence to the campaigns. To ensure that this objective is achieved, the study aimed to determine the audience's level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking, their level of exposure to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking, their other mediums for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking, their level of adherence to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking, and the extent to which the selected Facebook campaigns help in the fight against human trafficking.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The high level of poverty and the high cost of living in Nigeria have made many people desperate to make money at all costs. The means they resort to include but are not limited to human trafficking. In this illicit human trafficking business, the traffickers engage in the abduction, selling, and sexual exploitation of their victims, who are mostly women and children. In some cases, victims are tortured, used for rituals, or killed for organ harvesting. The traffickers also recruit unsuspecting members of the public who end up becoming part of a business they know nothing about. Among these recruits are civil servants and private health workers who often furnish them with information on how to avoid being caught and render professional and health services to them.

While all these happen, many families are rendered childless temporarily and permanently and are forced to spend a lot of money searching for their children and relatives who either became victims or recruits, respectively. Some go to the extent of seeking spiritual help from where they should not be seeking it, thereby adding to their problems. In the event that their children and relatives are rescued, learning of what human traffickers did to them can make some families engage in the same illicit business and hurt other people's children and relatives.

Despite the efforts by the Nigerian and Anambra state governments to tackle the ugly menace of human trafficking and the effects it has on the victims of the illicit trade, their families, and the country, human trafficking remains a serious problem in Nigeria and Anambra state in particular. Facebook and other social media platforms have been deployed in media campaigns by organizations and agencies, including NAPTIP, to fight this illicit business. Thus, in view of the aforementioned problems, the researcher decided to conduct this research to ascertain the audience level of exposure and adherence to NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.

1.3 Objectives of the study

To achieve the general objective of this study, which is to ascertain audience exposure and adherence to NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against human trafficking, the researcher sought to:

1. Determine the audience's level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking.
2. Examine the audience level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.
3. Identify other media for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking.
4. Ascertain the audience level of adherence to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.
5. Determine the extent to which Facebook campaigns help fight human trafficking.

1.4 Research questions

In line with the objectives, the study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the audience's level of awareness of human trafficking?
2. What is the level of exposure of the audience to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking?
3. What are other media for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking?
4. What is the audience level of adherence to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking?
5. To what extent do Facebook campaigns help fight human trafficking?

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Human Trafficking in Nigeria

Human trafficking is not new (Chia, 2018). Historically, it has taken many forms, but in the context of globalization, it has acquired shocking new dimensions. It is a complex, multi-faceted phenomenon involving multiple stakeholders at the institutional and commercial levels. It is a demand-driven global business with a huge market for cheap and commercial sex, which is often confronted with insufficient or unexercised policy frameworks or trained personnel to prevent it (Chia, 2018). He stated that Nigeria has acquired a reputation for being one of the leading African countries in human trafficking, both cross-border and internal.

A recent report by Ojugbana (2015) cited in Chia (2018) on human trafficking and migration to Europe shows that in 2014, 170,100 migrants arrived in Italy by sea, compared to 141,484 migrants who were ferried through the Mediterranean Sea from Libya in 2013. According to the report, the migrants came from Syria (42, 323), Eritrea (34, 329), Mali (9,908), Nigeria (9,000), Gambia (8, 691), Somalia (5, 756), and some other nations (4,095). Among the migrants, 64,625 applied for asylum (Ojugbana, 2015 cited in Chia, 2018). According to Ojugbana (2015) and Chia (2018), most migrants in Nigeria were victims of human trafficking hoodwinked by syndicates as a result of their desperation to travel to Europe or Asia for a better life. Thus, human trafficking is a complex phenomenon in which many people are involved at both the family and community levels, as well as at the border or in international transactions (Chia, 2018).

Oloko cited in Chia (2018) explained that human trafficking consists of both national and transnational recruitment and movement of persons for the purpose of providing cheap, manipulatable, and exploitable labor for domestic and agricultural work, commercial sex work or prostitution, begging, unregulated industrial work, and street trading.

The South-east and South-south geopolitical zones of Nigeria are known for their active involvement in human trafficking. For instance, several thousands of children have been trafficked from Igbo land, Akwa Ibom, and Cross River states to Lagos, Benin Republic, Togo, and Gabon for the purpose of engaging them in child labour, which is akin to child slavery (Chia, 2018, p. 5).

According to Njoku (2015), the high rate of child trafficking became a major source of concern for the Akwa Ibom State government, which banned "all forms of trafficking in children from the state to other parts of the country to serve as house-helps or cheap labour of any form" in 2004 and threatened to "deal drastically with parents who persist and promote trafficking in children."

The Western part of the country is also involved in child trafficking for using them as cheap labour for domestic work and agricultural production, including cocoa and rubber farms (Chia, 2018). Nwakamma (2004), cited in Chia (2018), reported that Asewele, a community in Ondo State, is a site of child slavery. He stated that both males and females were sold at a price of approximately N25, 000.00 each across the border and that there were always prospective buyers. He also noted that despite the efforts being made by the police and immigration officers, Nigerian borders are still vulnerable to child trafficking.

In Benin City, the capital of Edo State, syndicates specialized in recruiting and sponsoring young women to Europe, especially Italy, Amsterdam, and Belgium (Chia, 2018). Taire (2004) cited in Chia (2018) observed that it was since 2000 that the issue of Nigerian women in general, and ladies from Benin city and its environs in particular, going to Europe to work as commercial sex workers had become a real cause for concern since 2000. Similarly, *THIS DAY* (2004) cited in Chia (2018) in a story culled from *the Economist* stated that people-trafficking in Benin-city was an organized and lucrative trade. The paper observed that knowing how many ladies were shipped out each year was not possible, but “everyone in Benin-city knows who has gone.” The paper noted that the girls were recruited by local sponsors “who pay up-front for transport, and the girls therefore start out with thousands of dollars in debt.”

The major reasons for the persistence of the ugly phenomenon of human trafficking in Nigeria include pervasive poverty in the society, especially at the family level; the frightening problem of unemployment among the populace, particularly youths; and the ignorance of the fate of prospective victims of human trafficking in foreign countries (Chia, 2018). Some other reasons, according to him, include bad leadership that has failed to improve the welfare of the citizens, thereby resulting in mass disillusionment and the urge by many citizens to leave the country in search of better living conditions in other countries; the abuse of traditional methods of fostering children and the get-rich-quick syndrome in contemporary Nigerian society. The pressures of urban migration have also stretched the demands for house help and, in turn, induced the internal trafficking of young boys and girls conscripted sometimes into near slave labour (*The Guardian* Editorial, 2004 cited in Chia, 2018). Finally, there is the problem of the existence of powerful and influential syndicates within and outside Nigeria that coordinate and finance the despicable business, and the lure of huge profit that accrues to them annually from it (Chia, 2018).

2.1.2 Efforts of the Nigerian Government to Stop Human Trafficking

The future of many young people, especially women, has been frustrated, their dreams shattered, their destinies delayed, and their potentials caged because of the triumph of human trafficking, which often thrives in the shadow and silence of many and grows due to the three arms of government’s passive participation (Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020). Nigeria is a party to the protocol to prevent and suppress trafficking of persons, especially women and children (Trafficking Protocol), and punish offenders, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, as well as to a number of international human rights instruments, including the United Nations Slavery Convention (1927), the Convention for the Suppression of Trafficking in Persons and of the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others (1949), the ILO Forced Labour Convention (1930, N. 29), the ILO Abolition of Forced Labour Convention (1957, No. 105), and the ILO Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention (1999, No. 182) (United State Department of State 2015; Institute for Public Policy Research, 2013). According to them, Nigeria also ratified other international instruments, including the Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (1979), the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography (2000), and the Convention in the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families (1990), which have provisions that can apply by extension to the protection of the human rights of trafficked persons.

The National Agency for Prohibition of Traffic in Persons and Other Related Matters (NAPTIP) was established in 2003 to address the issue of trafficking (Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020). They pointed out that the Agency was

mandated to have specialized agencies, such as Investigation, Counseling and Rehabilitation, Public Enlightenment, and Legal and Prosecution. NAPTIP has 4Ps strategies which include (1) prevention, using strategic tools such as conferences, workshops, and mass media campaigns to promote awareness within Nigeria; (2) protection, involving rehabilitation and reintegration of victims into society through a National Referral mechanism for protection and assistance that was developed in 2013; (3) prosecution, investigating human trafficking cases, monitoring cross-border movements, and prosecuting trafficking cases in law courts; and (4) partnership, working in collaboration with other regional and international agencies or bodies that may ensure elimination and prevention of the root causes of the problem of trafficking in persons in Nigeria and in the boarding countries (NAPTIP 2018 cited in Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020; Institute for Public Policy Research, 2013).

The military and the government are making efforts during military joint action and registration to combat child and women trafficking and hostages (Ibrahim & Omoregbe, 2020).

2.2 Empirical Review

In a study to ascertain the perceived horrendous effects of child trafficking on children in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, Nnebedum and Ogugua (2022) adopted the cross-sectional survey method and used the Taro Yamane formula to determine the 400 respondents they studied. They used questionnaires and interviews to collect data. The authors analyzed the data using frequency tables/percentages and employed the Chi-square (X^2) statistic to test the study's hypotheses. This study found, among others, that child trafficking significantly affects the emotional state of children in the Ebonyi state. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, that government agencies, the media, non-governmental organizations, and stakeholders should embark on massive campaigns to create awareness of child trafficking. This study focused on what child trafficking does to children in Ebonyi state, while the current study focused on the level at which Anambra residents expose themselves and adhere to the Facebook campaigns against human trafficking by the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP).

To ascertain the socioeconomic impact of child trafficking on human security in Lagos State, Nigeria, Adedeji (2022) employed a qualitative and quantitative survey design and administered 200 copies of the questionnaire to 200 residents of four (4) Local Government Areas (Eti-Osa, Ibeju-Lekki, Lagos Island, and Ikeja) in Lagos State who were randomly selected for his study. He presented the data he collected using tables, absolute figures, and comparative percentages and analyzed the data using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version. From this study, he found that psychological trauma, disease and death, unwanted pregnancy, people having little education, and bad international image are the effects of child trafficking. Based on his findings, he recommended, among others, that both government and non-governmental organizations should focus their awareness on rural areas as they are easy targets of traffickers. This study was conducted in Lagos State, while the current study was conducted in Anambra State.

In their investigation of the effects of child trafficking on the educational development of youth in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria, Ihedioha (2022) employed the survey research design and administered 100 copies of the questionnaire to randomly selected teachers from different schools in Aba. From this study, she found that child trafficking leads to prostitution, addiction, cultism, low self-esteem, and involvement in truancy. Based on her findings, she recommended, among others, that teachers and school managers should create intense awareness using seminars, workshops, and training programs about what constitutes child abuse or trafficking. This study focused on the impact of child trafficking on the educational development of youths in Aba, Abia state, while the current study sought to ascertain the extent of exposure and adherence among Anambra residents to the NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.

Eze and Oli (2021) examined the socio-economic determinants of children's vulnerability to trafficking in Awka South Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. They adopted a mixed research design (survey and in-

depth interview) and used the multi-stage sampling procedure to select the samples they studied. Using the procedure, they selected 384 samples and administered them a structured questionnaire. They analyzed the data they collected from the survey using descriptive statistics such as frequency tables, simple percentages, and graphic illustrations and processed the data using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17. They also content-analyzed the data collected from the in-depth interviews. The study found, among others, that greed and poverty are major factors responsible for children's vulnerability to trafficking. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, that the government should implement genuine poverty alleviation programs in the society. This study focused on the factors that determine children's vulnerability to human trafficking, whereas the current study focused on the exposure and adherence to NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.

To determine the state and challenges of human trafficking in Nigeria and its implications for national peace and security, Abiodun, Akinlade, and Oladejo (2021) conducted a mixed research study (in-depth interview and descriptive survey research designs) and interviewed and administered questionnaires to 550 participants who were officers of the Nigeria Police, Nigeria Immigration Service, Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC), Ministry of Defense Corps (NSCDC), Ministry of Defense, the National Agency for Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP), National Boundary Commission (NBC), and other anti-human trafficking organizations at the state level in Nigeria. They purposively selected their samples from the six geopolitical zones of South South, South East, South West, North Central, North West, and North East Nigeria. From their study, they found, among others, that human trafficking has continued to thrive in Nigeria because of connivance from the security, immigration, embassy, online officials, and traffickers, while the menace has put Nigeria's identity black in the global system. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, that laws on human trafficking in the country should be strict and severe to offenders. This study focused on the challenges of human trafficking, whereas the current study focused on campaigns against human trafficking.

Umeonu, Chukwu-Okoronkwo, and Enyinnaya (2020) employed the survey research approach to examine the indispensable role of the media in the effort to address the issue of human trafficking and assess audience response to media coverage on the issue. They administered 100 copies of the questionnaire to the residents of central Amassoma and Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island/Alamco road and another 100 copies of the questionnaire to the media practitioners working within both areas. Umeonu *et al.* (2020) used the simple random sampling technique and simple percentage and frequency values to analyze the collected data. From their study, they found, among others, that the media has helped in sensitizing people about the scourge of human trafficking. Based on their findings, they recommended that the government should be committed to addressing issues concerning poverty, unemployment, gender-based abuse, and education. This study focused entirely on the media's role in the fight against human trafficking and audience response to it, while the current study specifically focused on how the NAPTIP uses Facebook to campaign against human trafficking, audience exposure, and adherence to the campaigns.

Azubuikwe and Iwarimie-Jaja (2019) examined the problem of human trafficking and its implications on the socioeconomic deprivation of victims and their families in Imo State by adopting a sequential exploratory mixed research design that constituted the triangulation of both qualitative and quantitative methods. The authors purposively selected 220 samples that they identified using the snowballing approach for their study and used KII, FGD, and a structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. They used content and thematic analysis for the qualitative data analysis and frequency tables and simple percentages for the quantitative data analysis. They also used the chi-square test to test their hypotheses. The study found, among others, that the trafficked position of victims of human trafficking in Imo State predisposes them to socioeconomic deprivation in form of labour exploitation, loss of household man-power, reduction in household income, poor health outcomes and inability to access basic services. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, that

the NAPTIP and sister agencies should engage in mass sensitization of the ills of trafficking to the public, especially in rural areas, to dissuade unsuspecting victims from being trafficked. This study was conducted in Imo State, whereas the current study was conducted in Anambra State.

In their analysis of precipitating factors and practices relating to trafficking in persons in Cross River State, Nigeria, Adi and Ngutor (2018) adopted the case study design and used purposive and snowball sampling techniques to select sixteen (16) victims of human trafficking for focus group discussion, 10 staff of the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP), and 5 staff of the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS) for key informant interviews, totaling 31 people. They reviewed, described, and summarized the data they collected from the discussions, transcribed the responses of the key informants, and discussed them based on whether they corroborated or contradicted the data from those who participated in the focus group discussion. , among others, that the factors responsible for human trafficking in their study area included economic motivation, poverty, search for employment, and lack of knowledge on human trafficking. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, that poverty alleviation programmes should be carefully initiated and implemented with real political will to reduce poverty among families and contain the vulnerability of young people to human trafficking in Cross River State. This study was conducted in Cross River State, whereas the current study was conducted in Anambra State.

Abdulraheem and Oladipo (2013) used quantitative and qualitative study designs to assess the pattern of trafficking in women and children and factors influencing it in Kwara State. They administered 800 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents they selected from eight (8) Local Government Areas of the state using a multi-stage sampling technique. Specifically, they administered 150 copies of the questionnaire to women and 50 copies to children and used interviews and focus group discussions to gather data. This study found, among others, that the majority of the trafficked children were girls, and poverty is a major contributing factor to trafficking in women and children. Based on their findings, they recommended, among others, the enactment of a comprehensive law that will tackle human trafficking and specify severe punishment for traffickers. This study was conducted in Kwara State, whereas the current study was conducted in Anambra State.

2.3 The theoretical framework

This study was anchored on the RAT and the encoding and decoding model.

Routine Activity Theory

RAT was pioneered by Cohen and Felson (1979) in an attempt “to understand patterns and upward trends of predatory criminal events in the historical context of changing economy” (Hsieh & Wang 2018). The theory holds that crime is likely to occur when there is a spatial-temporal convergence of three essential elements of crime, namely, a motivated offender, an attractive target, and the absence of capable guardianship (Tahir & Bernard, 2021). According to exponents of the theory (Cohen & Felson 1979; Maxfield 1987; Samonas 2013), motivated offenders are individuals who are capable and willing to commit a crime, while suitable targets can be a person or object that offenders consider vulnerable or attractive. On the other hand, guardianship, according to them, can be a person or an object that is effective in deterring offenses from occurring. The mere physical presence of guardianship in space and time can deter the committal of a crime (Tahir & Bernard, 2021). Routine activity theory is based on the following basic assumptions (Cohen & Felson 1979; Maxfield 1987; Felson & Cohen 1980):

A crime is likely to occur when there is a spatial-temporal convergence of three essential elements of crime, namely, a motivated offender, an attractive target, and the absence of capable guardianship.

Factors that render a particular target attractive are situational and crime-specific.

Crime can be perpetrated by anyone who has the opportunity in terms of capability and availability of vulnerable target;

Victims have choices on whether to be victims mainly by possibly avoiding situations where a crime can be committed against them.

Routine activity theory states that although there will always be a substantial number of motivated offenders, suitable targets (either vulnerable people or unattended valuables) and capable guardians (watchful friends and neighbors, the police, security personnel) will vary in terms of place and time (Ojedokun & Adeoti, 2022). Consequently, the risk of exposure to criminal victimization varies dramatically among the circumstances and locations in which people place themselves and their property (Schmalleger & Volk, 2018).

In relation to this study, the crime of human trafficking is being committed in Anambra State because there are people who are motivated to commit them, available and vulnerable targets who are often poor and ignorant and because of the absence of capable guardianship in some parts of the state where the crime is committed.

Encoding and decoding model

The encoding and decoding model of Stuart Halls is important for understanding audience interaction with the sender of a message and with the message itself (Ogundimu, 2013). The model emerged as a response to the traditional communication research, which viewed the sender, message, and receiver model of communication as being very “linear” in its interpretation of communication and a “mere circulation circuit” (Hall, 1980, p. 128). The encoding and decoding process begins with the producers (encoders) framing the message, while the readers (decoders) receive and interpret the meaning through interpretative frames drawn from their personal, cultural, and social background (Gurevitch, Scannell & Paddy, 2003 cited in Ogundimu, 2013; Aguayo, 2009 cited in Ogundimu, 2013). While the reader’s interaction with a text is active, the exchange is meaningful when the message is correctly decoded and produces the intended response from the reader because the broadcaster’s “meaning structures cannot always be equated with the audience’s “meaning structures” (Hall, 1980, p. 131).

Hall (2012) identified three hypothetical positions through which readers may construct meaning.

The first position is: “the dominant-hegemonic position where the audience is seen as accepting the connoted meaning in a message the way it is presented and decoding it within a framework of the dominant code or ideology.” Second is the negotiated position in which the audiences understand the dominant connotations in a text and accept or reject some aspects of codes, which sometimes include hegemonic definitions of “national interest or geopolitical views.” The third position is the oppositional code. Here, the audiences understand both the “literal and connotative inflection of a given discourse” but decode it in a contrary way” (p. 144).

In relation to this study, the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) may have produced and put out its campaigns against human trafficking on Facebook and Twitter (X), but the extent to which Anambra residents will expose and adhere to them could be determined by their hypothetical position and personal, cultural, and social background.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design, focusing on Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi in Anambra State with a combined 2006 National Population Commission census population of 953, 760. Using the Taro Yamane formula and the multi-stage sampling procedure, a sample size of 400 was determined and selected. A close-ended 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was used for data collection, while descriptive statistics (frequency tables, simple percentages, and mean) were used to analyze the data. In determining the response mean of the respondents, only mean scores of 2.5 and above were accepted, whereas mean scores of less than 2.5 were rejected.

4. FINDINGS

Section A: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1: Demographic data of respondents

Demographic Data	Frequency	Percentage
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Age		
18-30	81	20.3
31-41	292	73
42 and above	27	6.8
Gender		
Male	178	44.5
Female	222	55.5
Marital Status		
Single	211	52.8
Married	166	41.5
Separated	23	5.8
Widowed	0	0
Occupation		
Student	63	15.8
Farmer	36	9
Civil Servant	91	22.8
Trader	95	23.8
Tailor	14	3.5
Driver	29	7.3
Artisan	52	13
Fisherman	0	0
Others	20	5
Social media usage		
Yes	400	100
No	0	0
Facebook Usage		
Yes	400	100
No	0	0
Exposure to campaigns against human trafficking		
Yes	400	100
No	0	0
Exposure to NAPTIP's Campaigns against Human Trafficking		
Yes	400	100
No	0	0
Total	400	100

The table above shows that 20.3% of the 400 respondents are between 18 and 30 years old, while 73% are between 31 and 41 years old.. The remaining 6.8% are 42 years old and above..44.5% of the respondents were male, while 55.5% were female. Of the 400 respondents, 52.8% are single, while 41.5% are married.5.8% are separated, whereas none of the respondents are widowed. Regarding their occupation, 15.8% are students, while 9% are

farmers..22.8% are civil servants and 23.8% are traders. Regarding the occupation of the respondents, 3.5% are tailors while 7.3% are drivers..6.8% of the respondents are artisans, 5% have other occupations, and none are fishermen. Regarding the question of whether or not the respondents use social media, Facebook, and have been exposed to campaigns against human trafficking and the NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against the crime, all the respondents indicated that they use social media, Facebook, and have been exposed to the campaigns.

Section B: Analysis of Data on Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the audience's level of awareness of human trafficking?

Table 2- Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' level of awareness of human trafficking

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	U 3	D 2	SD 1	TOTAL	-- X	DECISION RULE
1	My level of awareness of human trafficking is very high.	50.5 202 1010	15 60 240	3.3 13 39	13.5 54 108	17.8 71 71	100 400 1468	3.7	Accepted
2	My level of awareness of human trafficking is high	31.3 125 625	10.5 42 168	5 20 60	24.8 99 198	28.5 114 114	100 400 1165	2.9	Accepted
3	My level of awareness of human trafficking is low.	9.3 37 185	2.8 11 44	18.3 73 219	39.3 157 314	30.5 122 122	100 400 884	2.2	Rejected
4	My level of awareness of human trafficking is very low.	7.3 29 145	8.8 35 140	22.5 90 270	46.8 187 374	14.8 59 59	100 400 988	2.5	Accepted

The table above shows how the respondents responded to the question regarding their level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking. On the question of whether their level of awareness is very high or not, 50.5% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of awareness is very high, while 15% agreed that their level of awareness is very high. Responding differently, 13.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that theirs is very high, while 17.8% strongly disagreed that theirs is very high. However, the remaining 3.3% were uncertain whether theirs is very high.

Answering the question on whether their level of awareness is high or not, 31.3% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of awareness is high, while 10.5% agreed that their level of awareness is high. Responding differently, 24.8% out of the 400 respondents that were studied disagreed that theirs is high while 28.5% strongly disagreed that theirs is high. However, the remaining 5% were uncertain whether theirs is high.

On the question of whether their level of awareness is low or not, 9.3% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of awareness is low, while 2.8% agreed that their level of awareness is low. Responding differently, 39.3% out of the 400 respondents that were studied disagreed that theirs is low while 30.5% strongly disagreed that theirs is low. However, the remaining 18.3% were uncertain whether theirs is low.

Regarding whether their level of awareness is very low or not, 7.3% out of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of awareness is very low, while 8.8% agreed that their level of awareness is very low. Responding differently, 46.8% of the 400 respondents disagreed that theirs is very low, while 14.8% strongly disagreed that theirs is very low. However, the remaining 22.5% were uncertain whether theirs is very low.

Based on the above findings, the respondents' level of awareness of human trafficking is very high. On the other hand, the mean scores of the responses of the respondents on their level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking that are 2.5 and above were accepted, while the one that is less than 2.5 was rejected.

Research Question Two: What is the audience level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking?

Table 3- Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	U 3	D 2	SD 1	TOTAL	-- X	DECISION RULE
5	My level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking is very high.	67.8 271 1355	5.3 21 84	1.5 6 18	16.5 66 132	9 36 36	100 400 1625	4.1	Accepted
6	My exposure level to the selected campaigns is high	52.8 211 1055	8 32 128	6.8 27 81	23.3 93 186	9.3 37 37	100 400 1487	3.7	Accepted
7	My exposure level to the selected campaigns is low	10.3 41 205	3.8 15 60	21.3 85 255	14.5 58 116	50.3 201 201	100 400 837	2.1	Rejected
8	My exposure level to the selected campaigns is very low	9.3 37 185	6.5 26 104	12.5 50 150	49 196 392	22.8 91 91	100 400 922	2.3	Rejected

The table above shows how the respondents responded to the question regarding their level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking. Regarding whether their level of exposure is very high or not, 67.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level is very high, while 5.3% agreed that their level is very high. Responding differently, 16.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that theirs is very high, while 9%

strongly disagreed that theirs is very high. However, the remaining 1.5% were uncertain whether theirs is very high.

Responding to the question on whether their level of exposure is high or not, 52.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of exposure is high, while 8% agreed that their level of exposure is high. Responding differently, 23.3% out of the 400 respondents disagreed that theirs is high, while 9.3% strongly disagreed that theirs is high. However, the remaining 6.8% were uncertain whether theirs is high.

Regarding whether their level of exposure is low or not, 10.3% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of exposure is low, while 3.8% agreed that their level of exposure is low. Responding differently, 14.5% out of the 400 respondents that were studied disagreed that theirs is low while 50.3% strongly disagreed that theirs is low. However, the remaining 21.3% were uncertain whether theirs is low.

On the question of whether their level of exposure is very low or not, 9.3% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their level of exposure is very low, while 6.5% agreed that their level of exposure is very low. Responding differently, 49% of the 400 respondents disagreed that theirs is very low, while 22.8% strongly disagreed that theirs is very low. However, the remaining 12.5% were uncertain whether theirs is very low.

Based on the above findings, the respondents' level of awareness of human trafficking is very high. On the other hand, the mean scores of the respondents' responses on their level of exposure to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking that are 2.5 and above were accepted, whereas those that are less than 2.5 were rejected.

Research Question Three- What are other media for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking?

Table 4- Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' exposure to other media for campaigns against human trafficking

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	U 3	D 2	SD 1	TOTAL	-- X	DECISION RULE
9	My medium of exposure to human trafficking campaigns is YouTube.	34 136 680	13.8 55 220	4.3 17 51	40.5 162 324	7.5 30 30	100 400 1305	3.3	Accepted
10	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is Facebook.	54.3 217 1085	9.8 39 156	10.5 42 126	15.5 62 124	10 40 40	100 400 1531	3.8	Accepted
11	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is Instagram.	31.3 125 625	4.8 19 76	5.5 22 66	25.5 102 204	33 132 132	100 400 1103	2.8	Accepted
12	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is Twitter.	24 96 480	6.8 27 108	13.3 53 159	32.5 130 260	23.5 94 94	100 400 1101	2.8	Accepted

13	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is the newspaper.	25.8 103 515	4 16 64	17.5 70 210	22 88 176	30.8 123 123	100 400 1088	2.7	Accepted
14	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is the magazine.	14.8 59 295	6.5 26 104	13.8 55 165	55.5 222 444	9.5 38 38	100 400 1046	2.6	Accepted
15	Word-of-mouth is my exposure medium to the campaigns	38.8 155 775	16.8 67 268	7 28 84	11 44 88	26.5 106 106	100 400 1321	3.3	Accepted
16	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is a billboard.	19.8 79 395	12.5 50 200	2.8 11 33	21.3 85 170	43.8 175 175	100 400 973	2.4	Rejected
17	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is radio.	43 172 860	11 44 176	5.8 23 69	32 128 256	8.3 33 33	100 400 1394	3.5	Accepted
18	My medium of exposure to the campaigns is television.	36.8 147 735	9 36 144	8.5 34 102	22.8 91 182	23 92 92	100 400 1255	3.1	Accepted

The table above shows the respondents' responses as it concerns other mediums that serve as their means of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking. As shown in the table, 34% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that their other medium of exposure to the campaigns is YouTube, while the remaining respondents strongly agreed that their other medium of exposure is Facebook (54%), Instagram (31.3%), Twitter (24%), newspaper (25.8%), magazine (14.8%), word-of-mouth (38.8%), billboard (19.8%), radio (43%), and television (36.8%). Again, out of the 400 respondents, 13.8% agreed that YouTube was their favorite, while the remaining respondents agreed that Facebook (9.8%), Instagram (4.8%), Twitter (6.8%), newspaper (4%), magazine (6.5%), word-of-mouth (16.8%), billboard (12.5%), radio (11%) and television (9%) were their favorite. As shown in the table, 40.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that YouTube is their medium of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking, whereas the remaining respondents disagreed that Facebook (15.5%), Instagram (25.5%), Twitter (32.5%), newspaper (22%), magazine (55.5%), word-of-mouth (11%), billboard (21.3%), radio (32%), and television (22.8%) are their media. Responding to the question of whether or not they strongly agree that

YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, newspaper, magazine, word-of-mouth, billboard, radio, and television are their other mediums of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking, 7.5% of the 400 respondents indicated that they strongly disagree that YouTube is their other medium of exposure to the campaigns, while the remaining respondents strongly disagreed that their other mediums are Facebook (10%), Instagram (33%), Twitter (23.5%), newspaper (30.8%), magazine (9.5%), word-of-mouth (26.5%), billboard (43.8%), radio (8.3%), and television (23%). Having stated the percentages of the respondents that strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, and strongly disagreed that YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, newspaper, magazine, word-of-mouth, billboard, radio, and television are respectively their other mediums of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking, 4.3% out of the 400 respondents that were studied were, however, uncertain as to whether or not their other medium of exposure to the campaigns is YouTube while the rest were also uncertain as to whether theirs are Facebook (10.5%), Instagram (5.5%), Twitter (13.3%), newspaper (17.5%), magazine (13.8%), word-of-mouth (7%), billboard (2.8%), radio (5.8), and television (8.5%).

Overall, the above findings show that the respondents' other mediums of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking are Facebook, radio, word-of-mouth, and television. Most of the respondents strongly agreed that they are the other mediums. On the other hand, the mean scores of the responses of the respondents on their other mediums of exposure to campaigns against human trafficking that are above 2.5 were accepted, while the one that is less than 2.5 was rejected.

Research Question Four: What is the level of adherence of the audience to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking?

Table 5- Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' level of adherence to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	U 3	D 2	SD 1	TOTAL	-- X	DECISION RULE
19	I always adhere to selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.	31.8 127 635	20 80 320	8.8 35 105	17.3 69 138	22.3 89 89	100 400 1287	3.2	Accepted
20	I sometimes adhere to selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.	63.5 254 1270	12.8 51 204	4.5 18 54	10.3 41 82	9 36 36	100 400 1646	4.1	Accepted

21	I rarely adhere to selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.	41.8 167 835	6 24 96	1.8 7 21	27.5 110 220	23 92 92	100 400 1264	3.2	Accepted
22	I do not adhere to selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking.	7.3 29 145	8.5 34 136	3.5 14 42	53.8 215 430	27 108 108	100 400 861	2.2	Rejected

The table above shows how the respondents responded to the question regarding their level of adherence to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking. Regarding whether they always adhere to the campaigns, 31.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that they always adhere to the campaigns, while 20% agreed that they always adhere to the campaigns. Responding differently, 17.3% of the 400 respondents disagreed that they always adhere to the campaigns, while 22.3% strongly disagreed that they always adhere to the campaigns. However, the remaining 8.8% were uncertain whether they would always adhere to the campaigns. Answering the question on whether or not they adhere to the campaigns sometimes, 63.5% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that they adhere to the campaigns sometimes, while 12.8% agreed that they adhere to the campaigns sometimes. Responding differently, 10.3% of the 400 respondents disagreed that they sometimes adhere to the campaigns, while 9% strongly disagreed that they sometimes adhere to the campaigns. However, the remaining 4.5% were uncertain whether they adhere to the campaigns.

Regarding the question of whether they rarely adhere to the campaigns, 41.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that they rarely adhere to the campaigns, while 6% agreed that they rarely adhere to the campaigns. Responding differently, 27.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that they rarely adhere to the campaigns, while 23% strongly disagreed that they rarely adhere to the campaigns. However, the remaining 1.8% were uncertain whether they would adhere to the campaigns.

Regarding whether or not they adhere to the campaigns, 7.3% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that they do not adhere to the campaigns, while 8.5% agreed that they do not. Responding differently, 53.8% of the 400 respondents disagreed that they do not adhere to the campaigns, while 27% strongly disagreed that they do not adhere to the campaigns. However, the remaining 3.5% were uncertain whether they would adhere to the campaigns.

Based on the above findings, the respondents sometimes adhere to the campaigns. On the other hand, the mean scores of the responses of the respondents on their level of adherence to Facebook campaigns against human trafficking that are above 2.5 were accepted, while the one that is less than 2.5 was rejected.

Research Question Five: To what extent do Facebook campaigns help fight human trafficking?

Table 6 - The extent to which Facebook campaigns help fight human trafficking

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	U 3	D 2	SD 1	TOTAL	-- X	DECISION RULE
23	Facebook campaigns always help fight human trafficking.	66.5 266 1330	4 16 64	6 24 72	13.8 55 110	9.8 39 39	100 400 1615	4.0	Accepted
24	The Facebook campaigns sometimes help in the fight against human trafficking.	61.8 247 1235	2.3 9 36	3.3 13 39	17.5 70 140	15.3 61 61	100 400 1511	3.8	Accepted
25	Facebook campaigns rarely help fight human trafficking.	5.8 23 115	12.5 50 200	22 88 264	22.5 90 180	37.3 149 149	100 400 908	2.3	Rejected
26	Facebook campaigns do not help fight human trafficking.	4.8 19 95	6.5 26 104	18 72 216	30.3 121 242	40.5 162 162	100 400 819	2.0	Rejected

The table above shows how the respondents responded to the question of the extent to which the selected Facebook campaigns help fight human trafficking. Whether the campaigns always help or not, 66.5% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that the campaigns always help in the fight, while 4% agreed that the campaigns always help in the fight. Responding differently, 13.8% of the 400 respondents disagreed that the campaigns always help in the fight, while 9.8% strongly disagreed that the campaigns always help in the fight. However, the remaining 6% were uncertain whether the campaigns always help in the fight against human trafficking.

Answering the question on whether or not the campaigns help in the fight sometimes, 61.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that the campaigns help in the fight sometimes, while 2.3% agreed that the campaigns help in the fight sometimes. Responding differently, 17.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that the campaigns help in the fight sometimes, while 15.3% strongly disagreed that the campaigns help in the fight sometimes. However, the remaining 3.3% were uncertain whether or not the campaigns help in the fight.

On the question of whether or not the campaigns rarely help in the fight, 5.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that the campaigns rarely help in the fight, while 12.5% agreed that the campaigns rarely help in the fight. Responding differently, 22.5% of the 400 respondents disagreed that the campaigns rarely help in the fight, while 37.3% strongly disagreed that the campaigns rarely help in the fight. However, the remaining 22% were uncertain whether or not the campaigns rarely helped in the fight.

Regarding whether or not the campaigns help in the fight, 4.8% of the 400 respondents strongly agreed that the campaigns do not help in the fight, while 6.5% agreed that the campaigns do not help in the fight. Responding differently, 30.3% of the 400 respondents disagreed that the campaigns do not help in the fight, while 40.5%

strongly disagreed that the campaigns do not help in the fight. However, the remaining 18% were uncertain whether the campaigns helped in the fight.

The respondents strongly agree that the campaigns always help in the fight against human trafficking. On the other hand, the mean scores of the respondents' responses on the extent to which the selected Facebook campaigns help in the fight against human trafficking were above 2.5 were accepted while the ones that are less than 2.5 were rejected.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This is a study on audience exposure and adherence to NAPTIP's Facebook campaigns against human trafficking. After conducting this research, some important findings were made. One of them is that Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents have a very high level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking. While their knowledge of the crime is beneficial, residents should also endeavor not to allow themselves to be lured into engaging in the crime either as traffickers or accomplices under any guise. They should also keep themselves updated on the modern methods that human traffickers use for their criminal operations. This is to ensure that they do not stand in the way of the Anambra State Government in its efforts to curb the crime in the State, especially since the State's Women and Social Welfare Commissioner, Ify Obinabo, was quoted by Ugwu (2023) to have said that the State Government was determined to prosecute child offenders in the State and has zero tolerance for human trafficking.

The second finding is that the Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' level of exposure to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking is very high. Without the campaigns being out there on Facebook in the form of communication, there would not have been an exposure in the first place. This is what communication can do and why Nwaolikpe (2018) believes that communication helps facilitate decision-making and policy-making for an improved environment. The National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) clearly understood this, which is why it communicated on Facebook using its campaign. Having mentioned the communication aspect of this finding, it is important to state that the residents were exposed to the campaigns because they are Facebook users. It shows that the NAPTIP got its campaign platform (Facebook) right.

The third finding of this study is that Facebook, radio, word-of-mouth, and television are Onitsha, Awka and Nnewi residents' other media for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking. This shows that residents of Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi do not depend on one source and one media platform to obtain information about and against human trafficking. In other words, as Obiaje and Adelabu (2022) put it: the audience of this era who actively add complexity to the range of information they consume by mixing media, media sources, and media activities, aided by technology. This finding is a call for the NAPTIP and other organizations that intend to embark on future campaigns against human trafficking to use these communication platforms to achieve an all-round goal of reaching a more diverse and heterogeneous audience. In the event that the organizations cannot afford to use all the platforms, the Federal and Anambra State Government should support them financially since it will only take Nigerians' collective efforts regardless of their status, tribe, religion, creed, and political affiliations to successfully stop human trafficking in and through Nigeria.

Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents only adhere to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking. McQuail (2010) argued that the multiplication of channels from the traditional linear model, i.e., one-way traffic communication by Harold Lasswell, which is sender-message-receiver, has given way to reverse transmission as it concerns the changing role of the sender to receiver and receiver to sender; but also the phase of the audience as an active user of what message is being communicated, how such message is decoded, in what context, to what effect, which in turn determines what and how the audience will encode as feedback. McQuail (2010) further argued that we are beginning to experience what is described as 'audience dictating and shaping' the media. It is this role of the audience (Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents) as active users of the NAPTIP's Facebook

campaign message against human trafficking, how they decoded the message and in the context they did and what they believe are the effects, that must have led to their decision to only adhere to the campaign sometimes. By playing this role, the residents dictate and shape the media since the campaign was put out on Facebook to attract and influence the residents.

The last but not least finding of this study is that Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents believe that the selected Facebook campaigns always help in the fight against human trafficking. This also points to how the selected campaigns were decoded. Believing that it always helps in the fight against human trafficking shows that they understood the campaign and what it is to fight.

CONCLUSION

Onitsha, Awka, and Nnewi residents' level of awareness of the menace of human trafficking is very high, as is their level of exposure to the selected Facebook campaigns against human trafficking. It was found that Facebook, radio, word-of-mouth, and television are the other mediums for exposure to campaigns against human trafficking, despite believing that the selected Facebook campaigns always help in the fight against human trafficking.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Residents of Anambra should always have the feeling to know more about human trafficking as that will make them not to ever stop exposing themselves to media campaigns against human trafficking.
2. Residents of Anambra should always adhere to campaigns against human trafficking.
3. Residents of Anambra should always reject any form of inducement to become human traffickers or accomplices.
4. Parents and guardians residing in Anambra State should always know the children's whereabouts and always prioritize their safety over financial gain.
5. The Federal and Anambra State Governments should lead the fight against human trafficking without leaving any stone unturned.

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